

Emergence of some cancers by evolutions of dark DNA in extra dimensions

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Recently, Hargreaves (*New Scientist*, Volume 237, Issue 3168, March 2018, Pages 29-31) has argued that some animal genomes seem to be missing certain genes, ones that appear in other similar species and must be present to keep the animals alive. He called these apparently missing genes by dark DNA. On the other hand, Sepehri and his collaborations (*Open Physics*, 16(1), pp. 463-475. Retrieved 11 Apr. 2019) has discussed that some biological events like DNA teleportation and water memory may be due to existence of some extra genes in extra dimensions. Collecting these results, we can conclude that origin of some cancers may be evolutions of dark DNA in extra dimension.

Keywords: Cancer, Dark DNA, extra dimensions, Water

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